

Urban Tourism Destination Image Through Characteristics Visitor: The Example of North Jakarta

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Abstract:- Every city in the world has its problems from simple to complex so various ways must be taken to push each city forward and have various achievements. However, the problem that occurs in the management of urban tourism is people's behavior, the extremely difficult issue of managing residents' attitudes toward tourism development in urban tourism destinations and finding effective solutions in how to manage residents' attitudes systematically to minimize residents' irritation in urban destinations, which are considered complex systems. A tourism destination cannot be separated from the image of the destination itself because visitors will see whether the destination to be visited has a positive or negative image. In addition, visitors will also be encouraged to visit a destination if the destination can attract visitors to have a variety of interesting activities and attractions. This article aims to present the destination image of urban tourism through the characteristics of visitors at Batavia PIK in North Jakarta. The research method in writing this scientific article uses quantitative methods by presenting the results of descriptive statistical processing of the frequency of the respondents' demographic data and the results of the average value of the dimensions of the destination image. The result presents the characteristics of visitor in tourism spot at Golf Island PIK mostly female, young visitor, private employed, bachelor, with the income below 3 million, and interesting to visit because of the culinary and unique photo spots in Golf Island PIK. And mostly visitor to visit on the weekend, mostly first timer to visit Golf Island, the most visitor came from West Jakarta, travel with family and the favorite spot is Pantjoran PIK. And the most visitor using Instagram to find information about tourism spot at Golf Island PIK.

Keywords:- *Urban Tourism; Destination Image; Visitor Characteristics.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Every city in the world has its problems from simple to complex so various ways must be taken to push each city forward and have various achievements. One way to encourage cities to be more advanced is through tourism, one of which is urban tourism. According to the UNWTO, urban tourism is "a form of tourist activity that takes place in an urban setting with intrinsic characteristics typified by non-agricultural based economy such as administration, manufacturing, trade, and services, as well as being nodal sites of transportation." According to the United Nations, 54 percent of the world's population lived in cities in 2015, and this figure is anticipated to rise to 60 percent by 2030. Tourism, along with other essential pillars, is a vital component in the economics, social life, and geography of many cities across the world, and is thus an important component in urban development programs. (UNWTO). However, the problem that occurs in the management of urban tourism is people's behavior, the extremely difficult issue of managing residents' attitudes toward tourism development in urban tourism destinations and finding effective solutions in how to manage residents' attitudes systematically to minimize residents' irritation in urban destinations, which are considered complex systems. (Stumpf et al., 2022). In addition to urban tourism, one of the tourism products that is being developed is rural tourism because it is an alternative to sustainable tourism in rural areas. Rural Tourism has a synergy with other economic activities, contributes to GDP and job creation, and capacity to encourage demand distribution in time (fight seasonality) and across a larger region, rural tourism has a strong potential to boost local economic growth and social transformation. (UNWTO). A tourism destination cannot be separated from the image of the destination itself because visitors will see whether the destination to be visited has a positive or negative image. In addition, visitors will also be encouraged to visit a destination if the destination can attract visitors to have a variety of interesting activities and attractions. In a virtual world, the perspective of the destination image is influenced by certain sociodemographic traits. (Rafael et al, 2017). This article aims to present the destination image of urban tourism through the characteristics of visitors at Batavia PIK in North Jakarta.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Destination Image

Destination images are divided into two dimensions there are cognitive images and affective images. (Jeong et al, 2012). The cognitive images such as activities, facilities, natural attractions, and cultural attractions. Also, the affective images such as exciting and relaxing. The other qualities of the destination image are significantly influenced by the cognitive image. (Santana et al, 2018). Recent studies that emphasize a particular picture of virtual destinations have also reported on the dimensions of cognitive and affective variables. (Rafael et al, 2017).

B. Urban Tourism

To create a better social life, there must be a synergy between the community in the development of urban tourism based on the nature of mutual collaboration. Changes in communal behavior are also crucial in this process. (Wahyuni et al., 2020). Realizing the development of urban tourism would be successful if the city government and the community collaborate to address key barriers such as destination governance integration and incompetent human resources. (Pattaray & Efendi, 2020). Adjustment of urban tourism land-use to create sustainable tourism traffic development. (Gao et al., 2021).

The following five characteristics are essential for the growth of urban tourism: (Zoreda 2012)

1. The government, public and commercial sectors, and residents should work together freely.
 2. Strategies should be developed to ensure that cities are visited several times.
 3. Urban places should be redesigned to include green areas.
 4. The city's transportation networks should be well-designed.
 5. The city should have an effective governance structure.
- Rural Tourism

III. METHODOLOGY

The research method in writing this scientific article uses quantitative methods by presenting the results of descriptive statistical processing of the frequency of the respondents' demographic data and the results of the average value of the dimensions of the destination image. The sample obtained as many as 247 respondents obtained from visitors to the tourist area at Golf Island Pantai Indah Kapuk, North Jakarta which includes Pantjoran PIK, The Cove at Batavia PIK and Urban Farm PIK. The destination image questionnaire uses a Likert scale with a score of 5 points Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Neutral (3), Agree (4) and Strongly Agree (5).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The result socio-economic of the respondents are presented in table 1. The were more female (56.7%) than male (43.3%) visitors in tourism spot. Most visitor are young 32% (18-25 years), 19.4% (34-41 years), 17.8% (26-33 years), 14.2% (42-49 years), 12.6% (>49 years) and 4% (<18 years). For the employment status most, visitor is private employed

(48.6%), 22.3% (students' college), 17% (others), 8.1% (self-employed), 3.2% (students) and 0.8% (government employed). The educational status most, visitor is Bachelor (44.9%), 22.7% (senior high school), 21.9% (diploma), 7.7% (postgraduate), 2% (junior high school) and 0.8% (doctoral). Monthly income of visitor the highest is visitor with monthly income below IDR 3 million (24.7%), 22.7% (IDR 3-6 million), 19.4% (IDR 6-10 million), 13% (others), 10.5% (above 15 million) and 9.7% (IDR 10-15 million).

TABLE 1. Characteristics Visitor of Socio-economic

Characters	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	107	43.3
	Female	140	56.7
Age	<18	10	4.0
	18 – 25	79	32
	26 – 33	44	17.8
	34 – 41	48	19.4
	42 – 49	35	14.2
	>49	31	12.6
Employment Status	Students	8	3.2
	Students	55	22.3
	College	120	48.6
	Private	2	0.8
	Employed	20	8.1
	Government	42	17
	Employed Self		
	Employed Others		
Educational Status	Junior High School	5	2.0
	Senior High School	56	22.7
	Diploma	54	21.9
	Bachelor	111	44.9
	Postgraduate	19	7.7
	Doctoral	2	0.8
	Others		
Monthly Income	< IDR 3 million	61	24.7
	IDR 3 – 6 million	56	22.7
	IDR 6 – 10 million	48	19.4
	IDR 10 – 15 million	24	9.7
	> 15 million	26	10.5
	Others	32	13

The result of visitor travel details is presented in table 2. There was more weekend (83.8%) than weekday (16.2%) time to visit. Most visitor are first time visitor (41.7%), 38.1% are 2-3 times, 11.3% are 4-5 times, 4.9% are 6-10 times and 4.0% are more than 10 times. The residential area of visitor mostly from West Jakarta (23.1%), 18.6% (Bogor), 13% (Tangerang), 10.5% (South Jakarta), 10.1% (North Jakarta), 6.9% (Bekasi), 6.5% (Depok), 5.3% (East Jakarta), 4% (Others) and 2% (Central Jakarta). For the travel company of visitor mostly with the family (56.3%), 22.7% with the friends, 13.8% with the partner, 4.9% alone, and 2.4% with the tour group. The Spot Location the favorite one is Pantjoran PIK (72.2%),

63,1% Cove at Batavia PIK and 44.8% Urban Farm. Media Awareness mostly visitor using Instagram (76.2%), 31% using Tiktok, 27.8% using YouTube, 20.2% using Facebook, 13.5% using Travel Blogs/Website, and 5.6% using Twitter.

TABLE 2. Visitor Travel details

Travel details	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Time of Visit	Weekday (Monday to Thursday)	40	16.2
	Weekend (Friday to Sunday)	207	83.8
Type of Visitor	First Time	103	41.7
	Visitor	94	38.1
	2 – 3 times	28	11.3
	4 – 5 times	12	4.9
	6 – 10 times	10	4.0
Residential Area	More than 10 times		
	Bekasi	17	6.9
	Bogor	46	18.6
	Depok	16	6.5
	West Jakarta	57	23.1
	Central Jakarta	5	2.0
	South Jakarta	26	10.5
	East Jakarta	13	5.3
	North Jakarta	25	10.1
	Tangerang	32	13.0
Others	10	4.0	
Travel Company	Partner	34	13.8
	Tour Group	6	2.4
	Family	139	56.3
	Alone	12	4.9
	Friends	56	22.7
Spot Location*	Cove at	159	63.1
	Batavia PIK	182	72.2
	Pantjoran PIK	113	44.8
	Urban Farm		
Media Awareness*	Twitter	14	5.6
	Instagram	192	76.2
	YouTube	70	27.8
	Facebook	51	20.2
	Tiktok	78	31
	Travel Blogs/Website	34	13.5

*Every respondent can answer more than 1 option

Destination image of urban tourism at Golf Island PIK North Jakarta presented in table 3. Based on the mean every factor the result presents the destination image of Urban Tourism in Golf Island PIK, North Jakarta the highest mean are visitors interesting to visit because of the culinary and unique photo spot. The second there are ornaments with an architectural style that is full of philosophy, distinctive colors, and inspiration that can be a place for tourism and education. The third about the atmosphere with a beautiful seaside view adds to the uniqueness and beauty. The fourth can be Urban Tourism. The fifth all activities related to urban tourism have been successfully managed. The sixth the management has

appropriated its role in developing tourism development in the community. The seventh about easy access. The eighth is availability of online public transportation facilities.

TABLE 3. Destination Image

Factor	Mean	Order*
Interesting to visit because of the culinary, unique photo spots	4.21	1
Easy access	3.91	7
Availability of online public transportation facilities	3.75	8
There are ornaments with an architectural style that is full of philosophy, distinctive colors, and inspiration that can be a place for tourism and education	4.19	2
The atmosphere with a beautiful seaside view adds to the uniqueness and beauty	4.16	3
Can be Urban Tourism	4.12	4
All activities related to urban tourism have been successfully managed	4.06	5
The management has appropriated its role in developing tourism development in the community	4.03	6

*Ranking order with increasing mean in the total sample

V. CONCLUSION

This article aims to present the destination image of urban tourism through the characteristics of visitors at Batavia PIK in North Jakarta. The result presents the characteristics of visitor in tourism spot at Golf Island PIK mostly female, young visitor, private employed, bachelor, with the income below 3 million, and interesting to visit because of the culinary and unique photo spots in Golf Island PIK. And mostly visitor to visit on the weekend, mostly first timer to visit Golf Island, the most visitor came from West Jakarta, travel with family and the favorite spot is Pantjoran PIK. And the most visitor using Instagram to find information about tourism spot at Golf Island PIK.

From the results obtained, it becomes the basis for implementing policies related to the development of urban tourism at Golf Island PIK North Jakarta, but there are several things that need to be considered to be able to increase tourism at Golf Island PIK North Jakarta, namely Availability of online public transportation facilities, Easy access and the management has appropriated its role in developing tourism development in the community. For further research, it can be investigated about the effect of destination image on visiting decisions.

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REFERENCES

- [1]. Chul Jeong & Stephen Holland (2012): Destination Image Saturation, *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 29:6, 501-519. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10548408.2012.701162>
- [2]. Gao, Y., Wang, D., Liao, Y., & Zou, Y. (2021). Relationship between urban tourism traffic and tourism land use: A case study of Xiamen island. *Journal of Transport and Land Use*, 14(1), 761–776. <https://doi.org/10.5198/JTLU.2021.1799>
- [3]. Pattaray, A., & Efendi, M. N. (2020). Urban Tourism Development: Constraints and Expected Changes of Kota Lama Tourism Area (KLTA) in Surabaya, Indonesia. *Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Management*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.15640/jthm.v8n1a14>
- [4]. Rafael, C. S. & Almeida, A. R. (2017). Socio-demographic Tourist Profile and Destination Image in Online Environment. *Journal of Advanced Management Science*. 5 (5). <https://doi:10.18178/joams.5.5.373-379>
- [5]. Santana, L. D & Gosling, M. S. (2018). Dimensions of Image: A Model of Destination Images Formation. *Journal of Tourism Analysis*, 23, pp. 303-322. <https://doi.org/10.3727/108354218X15305418666940>
- [6]. Stumpf, P., Lusticky, M., Vojtko, V., & Jakulin, T. J. (2022). Systems approach to residents' irritation in urban tourism destinations.
- [7]. Wahyuni, I. A. M., Weni, I. M., & Hariyanto, T. (2020). SOCIAL BEHAVIOR OF URBAN TOURISM DEVELOPMENT. *International Journal of Business and Applied Social Science*, 15–21. <https://doi.org/10.33642/ijbass.v6n5p2>
- [8]. Zoreda, J. L. (2012). Birleşmiş Milletler Dünya Turizm Örgütü Kent Turizmi Küresel Zirvesi, Ekonomik ve Sosyal Gelişime Katkısı, İstanbul, <http://haber.tobb.org.tr/ekonomikforum/2012/10/016-021.pdf>.
- [9]. UNWTO—United Nations World Tourism Organization. Product Development: Urban Tourism. Available online: <https://www.unwto.org/urban-tourism> (accessed on 22 June 2022)